

Religion Identity and Academic Achievement Among Junior High School Students

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the connection between religious identity and academic achievement in junior high school students. Recent research shows a strong link between religiosity and academic success. However, some research argues that this link is caused by familial and social factors, such as disparities in family capital levels among religious affiliations. Whether or not religious variables influence adolescent academic achievement may also depend on whether or not their parents and children share the same religious beliefs. It looked at the relationship between adolescents' religion, their parents' religiosity, and academic accomplishment in the context of family and community capital. According to the findings, family social capital is largely responsible for the relationship between students' religiosity and academic success, whereas the relationship between academic success and religious homogamy between parents and adolescents is unrelated to family and community social capital. Parents with high levels of religiosity and adolescents with low levels of religiosity are more likely to have low accomplishments.

Keywords: *religious identity, academic achievement, junior high school students*

Author's Bionote:

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